

Smart bins for enhanced resource recovery and sustainable urban waste practices in smart cities: A systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

Waste collection bins with smart capabilities play a crucial role in contemporary urban landscapes, forming integral components of efficient and sustainable waste management practices worldwide. This paper conducts a thorough review of state-of-the-art smart bins, emphasizing advanced features such as material separation and integrated automation. The analysis, based on 79 selected articles from a pool of over 1400 publications, underscores critical gaps in the existing literature. While a widely accepted common ground that outlines the definition for smart bins exists, in the form of waste disposal containers incorporating functionalities such as fill-level monitoring and IoT connectivity, this research identifies substantial areas for improvement. Specifically, material separation practices, including automated waste segregation, and the overall maturity of conceptual frameworks present significant challenges, hindering the optimization of resource recovery essential for pioneering circular economy models. Moreover, a lack of uniformity and standardization in automation techniques is apparent across studies. Various articles propose divergent approaches, each with distinct advantages and drawbacks. Notably, no unified solution emerges that could harness collective strengths and mitigate shortcomings. Identifying these issues is paramount for advancing the field and tackle sustainability-related challenges within modern smart cities.

1. Introduction

Waste production inevitably follows urbanization, economic progress, and population increase in modern societies. As the population density rises in economically thriving countries and cities, an expanded array of products and services becomes available to their citizens, leading to larger volumes of waste that require management, proper treatment, and safe disposal (Silpa et al., 2018). This growth makes effective management of the generated waste a serious challenge for developed and developing countries. The current state of waste management is a pressing issue, especially in urban settings where waste production rates have reached unprecedented levels (Tiseo, 2023). Indicatively, in the United States of America, municipal waste generation has witnessed a staggering increase over the past six decades. This escalation is evident in both absolute numbers and per capita measurements, clearly underscoring the gravity of the situation. From 1960 to 2018, municipal waste production surged by approximately 231.3 million tons, marking a striking increase of over 262 %. Over the same period, per capita waste generation escalated by 2.22 pounds per day,

representing a substantial rise of approximately 83 % (Tiseo, 2020, 2022).

As the rapid urbanization and industrialization trends observed in recent years have significantly contributed to this surge in refuse production, the accumulation of waste materials presents considerable challenges for disposal and treatment, which current waste management practices fail to address adequately. A rather recent trend referred to as “overtourism”, characterized by an excessive influx of tourists to popular destinations, poses a significant challenge to waste management as well exacerbated by its contribution to waste generation, necessitating urgent mitigation measures (Remenyik et al., 2021). Tourists play a pivotal role in the escalation of waste production, evidenced by their considerable impact on waste generation patterns (Pandey et al., 2023). Notably, in certain tourist destinations, waste generation reaches its zenith during peak seasons, underscoring the correlation between tourism activity and waste accumulation (Koliotasi et al., 2023; Martins & Cró, 2021). Insufficient waste management infrastructure, sub-optimal collection systems, and limited recycling facilities exacerbate the problem, resulting in improper waste disposal practices such as open

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burning, illegal dumping, and unregulated landfilling (Kaur et al., 2021; Konstantinidis, Sifnaios, Arvanitakis, et al., 2023). One of the major consequences of poor waste management is the potential outbreak of diseases, as accumulated waste acts as a breeding ground for pathogens and attracts disease-carrying vectors, leading to the spread of infections among both humans and animals (Krystosik et al., 2020). In addition, the release of hazardous chemicals from uncontrolled waste disposal sites can cause soil and water source contamination, and the surrounding environment, leading to long-term health risks (Abubakar et al., 2022).

The introduction of circular economy models in contemporary societies and their seamless adoption can beneficially impact urban waste management. Circularity describes an economic framework where products, components, and materials flow in an ideally closed loop, aiming to maximize utility and value, while minimizing discarded items and overall waste (Bourguignon, 2016). In terms of waste handling, circularity refers to promoting sustainable practices that reduce waste generation, encourage recycling, and foster resource efficiency, targeting an environmentally friendly and economically viable approach. In this context, emphasis is given to separating waste into distinct streams that include organic waste, recyclables, and hazardous materials. This segregation facilitates more effective handling schemes and recycling processes, allowing for valuable resources to be recovered, reducing the need for raw material extraction, and minimizing the environmental impact associated with waste generation.

Within this realm of sustainability and to tackle the challenges encountered by conventional waste management, the concept of smart bins has emerged as part of a promising solution framework (Konstantinidis et al., 2022). Smart bins, alternatively referred to as intelligent waste bins are innovative waste containers that integrate technology combinations, such as sensors, data analytics, and automation to revolutionize litter handling. These bins facilitate real-time monitoring of waste levels inside the container, collection route optimization, and promotion of efficient refuse disposal strategies. Furthermore, incorporating robot-based modules and various combinations of sensors and actuators offers the possibility of real-time material separation (Konstantinidis, Sifnaios, Tsimiklis, et al., 2023).

This paper aims to explore the concept and features of smart bins, establish the state-of-the-art (SotA) and identify possible gaps in academic research. The goal is to determine the role of intelligent disposal units in promoting circularity by integrating in-situ material separation functionalities within the context of a sustainable future for modern communities. Toward this goal, the specific objectives for this review are as follows:

1. Identify the SotA regarding smart bins, including their capabilities, approaches, and applied technologies.
2. Investigate and assess material separation capabilities in conjunction with smart bins.

2. Related work

Although the concept of smart bins is relatively new, with most relevant references dating back no more than the last decade, this subject that has drawn the attention of various researchers. Soni and Kandasamy (2018) published a survey on smart garbage bin systems. The article presented various existing solutions at the time in a comprehensive, yet unstructured manner. Approximately 30 references were cited, adequately covering the state of the art at the time, particularly significant given the scarcity of relevant publications, as highlighted in the Results section of this current study. Within the survey, 15 distinct cases of bins with intelligent monitoring were identified and discussed and 4 more cases focused on smart route planning and optimization for trash collection. Nevertheless, only a single case that implemented waste segregation was identified and the article's attention appeared to shift away from the examination of actuator inclusion, investigation of the

type of waste input, and integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in smart bin systems, instead focusing on IoT-enabled waste management systems.

Sirsat and Bardekar (2021) published a similar study, although covering a narrower range of identified cases, focusing on 15 prominent instances. Similar to the previous study, this review also presented its findings in an unstructured form and primarily emphasized IoT-enabled solutions. However, it did provide a clear statement about the potential for improvement in the field of smart bins. Additionally, the paper raised inquiries about existing solutions concerning waste classification for improved recycling and offered insight into existing system costs, although an expanded reference pool could further strengthen the study.

A more inclusive review conducted by Noiki et al. (2021), explored the potential of smart bins to enhance urban waste management in response to the escalating urbanization trend, which has led to a significant surge in waste generation in modern cities. The study comprehensively examined over 25 identified cases of smart bins, categorized into 5 distinct groups. The review recognized numerous improvements and innovations in the field, indicating promising results. However, the study did identify a bottleneck in the wide application of smart bin technologies, resulting in relatively low adoption rates. This challenge mandates the development of tailor-made solutions to suit the unique characteristics of different urban settings. To strengthen the research, more sources are required, particularly in the identification of a broader range of smart bin case studies, emphasizing their distinct features and capabilities. The review also highlighted that the implementation costs of smart bins remain high, but it would be beneficial to delve further into this statement and provide a more detailed analysis of the factors that contribute to these costs. Additionally, the review primarily emphasized IoT-enabled smart bins with data transfer capabilities and did not elaborate on waste separation capabilities and the reasons behind the scarcity of relevant cases in this area, akin to previous studies. Exploring this aspect further would enhance the completeness of the study and provide valuable insights into potential advancements in waste separation technologies.

A comprehensive and well-structured study on city-level solid waste management (SMW), through a systematic literature review, was conducted by Sosunova and Porras (2022). The review aimed to build a holistic image of city-level SWM practices, also investigating smart bins, but not as its main focus. By encompassing a substantial dataset, and analyzing over 170 relevant literature sources, the study efficiently extracted data on the presence of hardware in smart garbage bins. This meticulous approach allowed for extensive mapping of various sensors and actuators used in existing applications. While the study sufficiently outlines integrated hardware and presents the applied technologies in a comprehensive holistic graph, it does not opt to offer in-depth insights into segregation and classification techniques and different approaches. Furthermore, the subject of different waste inputs in various smart bin case studies or proposing a unique concept for a smart bin was not addressed in the review. Nevertheless, the study contributes significantly to understanding city-level SWM practices and the role of smart bins, laying a solid foundation for further research and potential advancements in the field.

From an alternative perspective, Wu et al. (2023) investigated the utilization of artificial intelligence, specifically convolute neural networks (CNN) for intelligent waste identification and recycling (IWIR), addressing a notable gap in previous research. The study provides valuable insight in terms of the applied classification categories, such as plastics, e-waste, and other types of waste in a thorough and well-structured approach, examining over 300 relevant articles. While the review proves quite insightful in its emphasis on visual recognition, it does not explore alternative recognition methods based on the chemical composition of discarded items. Additionally, the practical implementation of the presented approaches, such as smart bins or material recovery facilities (MRFs), was not discussed. Nevertheless, it contributes significantly to the understanding of waste classification and

intelligent waste management and lays the groundwork for future investigations in utilizing AI technologies for more efficient and sustainable recycling practices.

Concluding this section, an examination of related work in the field of smart bins has shed light on the research problem existing in the literature pertaining to smart bins and waste management. The limited number of examined papers and reviews in this novel field mandates the need for further exploration and in-depth investigations. While the majority of the existing studies focus on IoT-enabled smart bins, a noticeable gap remains in the understanding of waste separation techniques and the different waste input variations for the various existing cases. Sorting techniques, mainly centered around visual recognition, lack sufficient exploration of composition-based classification methods.

3. Methodology

To address the objectives defined in Section 2 two main research questions are formulated:

1. **Research Question 1:** What sensing and actuating technologies are utilized in smart bins for urban waste management?
2. **Research Question 2:** What segregation capabilities are offered by the currently employed solutions with regard to smart bins for urban waste management?

A systematic literature review (SLR) protocol is proposed, to provide a comprehensive and well-structured approach to identifying and summarizing papers that examine smart bins design, deployment, and evaluation in urban environments. A step-by-step methodology is followed, presented by Tranfield et al. (2003), that divides the study into 3 distinct stages, and a further total of 9 phases.

3.1. Stage I - planning the review

This stage initiates the SLR process and includes three phases.

Phase 0 - Recognizing the review necessity. The *Related Work* section provides compelling evidence of the significant potential of smart bins in the field of urban waste management. However, it also reveals and highlights gaps in the existing research, underscoring the necessity for a dedicated study to address these gaps comprehensively.

Phase 1 - Preparing the review proposal. The search for relevant articles will be conducted across three different databases, namely the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Xplore, Scopus, and the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM). These databases were selected as prominent sources of published articles in technical fields, such as the area of solid waste management (SWM). The search was conducted on June 28, 2023. Following a preliminary screening that indicated that a substantial number of relevant articles was published in the last decade, it was decided that publications between January 2008 and June 2023 will be included in the search to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive perspective. As a result, works published after the latter date will not be included in this study.

Phase 2 - Developing the review protocol. The review adheres to the PRISMA framework as proposed by Liberati et al. (2009) and further elaborated by Page et al. (2021), to ensure transparency, repeatability and consistency via a standardized methodology that boasts high credibility.

3.2. Stage II - conducting the review

This stage, consisting of set of 5 additional phases, formulates the research query, explores the selected libraries, and establishes the inclusion and quality criteria to initiate and conclude the screening, serving as the basis for the narrative analysis in the *Results* Section.

Phase 3 - Identification of Research. The keywords used for the search in each database were selected based on the research questions and focused on three main domains: the general field of research, waste, and containers. Therefore, by combining the list of keywords in a single alphanumeric string connected by boolean operators the following search query was formed:

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("sustainability" OR "smart cities" OR "IoT") AND ("bin" OR "disposal unit" OR "waste container" OR "dumpster") AND ("waste" OR "recycling" OR "waste management" OR "waste disposal").
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The use of conjunction operators (AND) aims to refine the search to articles that cover all three main areas, while disjunction operators (OR) expand the query to encompass various alternative nomenclatures for the main search items. Every database search was conducted within the article title, abstract, and metadata.

Phase 4 - Selection of Studies. The conducted search produced a total of 1427 papers. More specifically, 386 publications were returned from IEEE Xplore, 673 from Scopus, and 368 from the ACM database. A graphic overview of the study process is illustrated in Fig. 1, according to the adhered to PRISMA guidelines. Following the filtering out of duplicated articles, a total of 1182 remain for further assessment. Additionally, by excluding papers that did not meet the established inclusion criteria presented in Table 1, as well as removing non-publicly available works the definitive number of included publications came down to 144.

Phase 5 - Study quality assessment. In addition to the initial screening process, the chosen articles underwent an elaborate quality assessment to ensure a review of the highest quality. To achieve this, a quality criteria checklist was generated and presented in Table 2. Four specific questions were devised, focusing on the current state of smart bins and waste separation. The criteria were applied in a pass/fail manner, whereby only papers that satisfied at least 2 were considered for further evaluation. As a result of this procedure, the final number of publications deemed eligible for the final analysis amounted to 79.

Phase 6 - Data extraction and monitoring. In pursuit of gathering essential information for evaluating the systems described within each publication and comprehensively understanding their architectural components and applications in urban waste management, two distinct sets of data were gathered. The first set focuses on examining the context, providing key insights into the capabilities of smart bins and the specific environments in which they operate. This set also encompasses qualitative data, considering material input and trash separation. The data collection process adheres to a predefined extraction form presented in Tables 3 and 4, which enables the comprehensive recording of data from the primary studies used to address the research questions. An additional set of data focusing on the sensors and actuation mechanisms was also collected for analysis. Zotero was employed as a robust reference management tool throughout the screening, quality assessment, and data extraction stages. To facilitate storing, analyzing, and visually representing the retrieved data points from each publication, as well as facilitating reporting and dissemination, a spreadsheet was utilized.

Phase 7 - Data synthesis. The data points presented in Tables 3 and 4 are extracted from the content of the publications, forming the basis for subsequent analysis and addressing the research questions.

3.3. Stage III - reporting and dissemination

In the final stage of the SLR, the analysis is performed in order to

Fig. 1. The interconnected blocks of the PRISMA approach (Liberati et al., 2009; Page et al., 2021) combined with Tranfield's quality criteria (Tranfield et al., 2003). As the proposed systematic literature review progresses, the number of selected articles decreases at each stage. In the end, a total of 79 out of 1427 articles remain.

Table 1
Inclusion and exclusion criteria performed in Stage II - Performing a review.

Inclusion (Must...)	Exclusion (Must not...)
...be published between 2008 and 2023.	...be published before 2008
...be written in English, in understandable language.	...be written in any other language except English
...focus on primary studies in waste management applications that include the utilization of smart bins, methodologies, concepts, and validation.	... be secondary studies such as reviews, book chapters, or grey literature.
...refer to research on waste management in an urban setting.	...refer to waste management in other settings, such as industrial, construction, or healthcare.
...be published in journals, conferences, symposiums, and workshops, following a peer-to-peer review process.	... be published in the form of an abstract, short paper, conference keynote, proposal, lecture notes, editorial, or tutorials

comprehensively investigate the subject and answer the research questions using the information produced through data synthesis.

Phase 8 - Report and recommendations. Considering the guidelines by Tranfield et al. (2003), based on the data spreadsheet and the presented narrative study, the descriptive and thematic analyses are constructed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3, respectively. The former is conducted to portray a contemporary mapping of the selected records, whereas the latter provides an in-depth look at major themes of interest identified during the review when answering the given questions.

Phase 9 - Getting evidence into practice. In this final phase, the gathered knowledge of the conducted procedures and analyses is used to

Table 2
Quality criteria for the study selection.

Assessment criteria	
QA1	Are the sensing and actuating technologies described in the publication clearly explained and supported with relevant up-to-date information and technical details?
QA2	Does the publication provide a comprehensive description with regard to the design and development of smart bins?
QA3	Do the employed solutions for waste segregation discussed in the publication offer detailed information on their capabilities, effectiveness, and real-world implementation?
QA4	Does the publication provide valuable insight into the challenges, opportunities, or advancements related to waste separation/segregation in smart bins for waste management?

propose an innovative solution that bridges the gaps by addressing identified weaknesses in the research.

SLR conducted with the PRISMA methodology was selected for this study due to its robustness and comprehensive nature in reviewing the literature. Nonetheless, SLR encounters notable limitations. Investigating solely open-access papers may introduce bias, as it may overlook relevant studies published in subscription-based journals. Furthermore, comparing studies with diverse methodologies poses a challenge, requiring careful consideration to ensure a valid synthesis of findings. Variations in study design, participant demographics, intervention protocols, and outcome measures can potentially hinder direct comparisons and may necessitate cautious interpretation of the results. Therefore, while SLRs with PRISMA methodology offer valuable insights, researchers must remain cognizant of these limitations to ensure a comprehensive and unbiased synthesis of the literature. This is

Table 3
Data extraction points per examined paper.

#	Study data item	Description	Relevant RQ
1	Reference	Unique ID for the study.	Study Overview
2	Year	Publication year of the paper.	Study Overview
3	Category	Category of the problem that the paper dealt with.	RQ1, RQ2
4	Environment	Environment where the bin operates in (Indoor, Outdoor)	RQ1, RQ2
5	Sensing	Y/N	RQ1
6	Waste separation	Y/N	RQ2
7	Waste input type	Type of waste input: Dry, wet, organic, recyclable, mixed	RQ1
8	Waste input form	Type of waste input form: Single item, Multiple items of a single group, Mixed.	RQ2
9	Waste separation type	Type of waste separation: dry from wet, metals, plastics, recyclables.	RQ2
10	Concept maturity	Rough Technology Readiness Level (TRL) categorization: Low, Medium, High.	RQ1

Table 4
Data extraction points per examined paper regarding smart bins sensing and data transfer capabilities.

#	Study data item	Description
1	Fill level sensor	Presence and type
2	Gas sensor	Y/N
3	Weight sensor	Y/N
4	Environment sensor	Y/N
5	RFID	Y/N
6	IoT compatibility	Y/N
7	Artificial Intelligence	Y/N
8	GPS	Y/N
9	GSM	Y/N
10	WIFI	Y/N
11	Other sensors	Presence and type
12	Compaction	Y/N
13	Shredding	Y/N

achieved through meticulous screening and assessment methodology to achieve a diverse pool of high-quality publications, enhancing the reliability of the review process and addressing the aforementioned possible shortcomings.

4. Results

4.1. Narrative analysis

The literature review revealed that papers relevant to the topic of smart bins can be classified into five primary categories:

4.1.1. Prototype development (61 %)

The majority of the papers were categorized in this group, discussing the design and fabrication of smart bin prototypes with varying functionalities. A number of papers in this category described the fabrication of basic smart bin prototypes, equipped with essential smart functionalities, such as fill-level sensors and data transmission routes to alert collection crews when the bins required emptying (Sai et al., 2023; Shanthini et al., 2022; Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022). Other cases presented more advanced prototypes, incorporating additional capabilities, such as gas detectors (Anbumani et al., 2021; Jimeno et al., 2021; Likotiko et al., 2023; Mohamed et al., 2023; Mohiuddin et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Pagar et al., 2022; Sampredo et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2019) and environment (Bhuvanewari et al., 2022; Chung et al., 2020;

Singh et al., 2019).

In the context of waste separation, several papers showcased smart bins with multiple compartments, enabling different segregation scenarios, by mechanically controlling the lids of the distinct containers (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Balbin et al., 2021; Bhuvanewari et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2023, 2019; Singh et al., 2019; Kamrul et al., 2021; Longo et al., 2021). Some of these prototypes took the form of compact reverse vending machines with internal to align the entry point with the correct compartment through linear (Selvakumar et al., 2022; Makhseed et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023) or rotary mechanisms (Baras et al., 2020; Chung et al., 2020; Jimeno et al., 2021; Leon et al., 2020; Maulana et al., 2018; Mohammed et al., 2022; Sirawattananon et al., 2021; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017), thus facilitating routing for waste sorting.

Among the various cases, some unconventional concepts were identified. For instance, Deeksha et al. (2018) integrated a desktop-sized robot arm into a multi-bin setup to perform material handling. Another study by Zhao et al. (2017) introduced a vibration-based mechanism for predicting fill levels. Additionally, another group deployed a movable bin programmed to autonomously reach the collection point upon filling (Anbumani et al., 2021).

The majority of encountered cases also appeared to demonstrate IoT compatibility, with Leon et al. (2020) being the sole exception in this group. Data transfer emerged as a crucial aspect of smart bins, with different protocols utilized to address various situations. Notably, implemented LoRa to overcome large distances without intermediary hardware (Chung et al., 2018, 2020; Ramson et al., 2022; Sheng et al., 2020; Zebua et al., 2022; Ziouzos & Dasygenis, 2019). Additionally, GSM was present in some cases as an alternative to WIFI when the latter was unavailable (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ahmed et al., 2022; Ayi-Annum et al., 2022; Badotra et al., 2021; Chung et al., 2018; Deeksha et al., 2018; Jain et al., 2023; Mohiuddin et al., 2021; Mustapha et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Prasad et al., 2018; Ramson et al., 2022; Rohit et al., 2018; Sampredo et al., 2021; Tamakloe & Rosca, 2020; Widiastiwati & Satria, 2020; Wijaya et al., 2017; Xenya et al., 2020). Furthermore, artificial intelligence played a significant role in smart bins, either in conjunction with computer vision for object classification in numerous instances (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Antora et al., 2022; Baras et al., 2020; Boubaris et al., 2022; Dasari et al., 2021; Hojjati et al., 2022; Jacobsen et al., 2020; Jain et al., 2023; Jimeno et al., 2021; Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019; Longo et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Pagar et al., 2022; Pan et al., 2018; Sampredo et al., 2021; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017; Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022; Ziouzos et al., 2021) or as a predictive analysis tool for fill-level (Alwis et al., 2022; Likotiko et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2017).

4.1.2. Subsystem development(6 %)

This category exhibited a primary focus on incorporating and testing specific subsystems within intelligent waste disposal units, rather than the containers as a whole. The majority of instances within this category explored the integration of optical camera-based modules for object recognition, particularly for e-waste classification (Antora et al., 2022; Sampredo et al., 2021) and recognition of recyclables (Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022). Amores et al. (2015) presented the implementation of a multiple gas sensor module to monitor organic waste degradation, detect odor-specific compounds, and dispense a masking fragrance to mitigate bad odors until trash collection. Kokoulin and Kiryanov (2019) demonstrated the integration of an optical subsystem on a reverse vending machine (RVM) dedicated to classifying recyclable containers using computer vision and neural networks.

4.1.3. Sensor integration (5 %)

This class represented a highly targeted approach, centering on the integration and testing of specific sensors on intelligent bins. Although this category may appear as a subset of the previous ones, it is noteworthy to acknowledge that the publications grouped here have the

Table 5

Contextual information about the surveyed articles, including the category (Cat.) of the problems, the placement environment (Env.) of the smart bin, and overall Sensing & Actuation (Act.) capabilities. Categories include: Prototype Development (P.D.), Sub-system Development (S.D), IoT application (IoT), Case Study (C.S.), and Sensor Integration (S.I.)

Citation	Cat.	Env.	Sensing	Act.
(Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020)	P.D.	Mixed	Y	Y
(Ahmed et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Ali et al., 2020)	IoT	N/A	Y	N
(Als bou et al., 2018)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Alwis et al., 2022)	IoT	Indoors	Y	Y
(Amores et al., 2015)	S.D.	N/A	Y	N
(Anbumani et al., 2021)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Antora et al., 2022)	S.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Aravindaraman & Ranjana, 2019)	S.I.	Indoors	Y	N
(Ayi-Annum et al., 2022)	IoT	N/A	Y	Y
(Azarudeen et al., 2021)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Badotra et al., 2021)	IoT	Indoors	Y	Y
(Balbin et al., 2021)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Baras et al., 2020)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Bhuvaneswari et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Boubaris et al., 2022)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Burman et al., 2022)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Chung et al., 2020)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Chung et al., 2018)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Das et al., 2021)	S.I.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Dasari et al., 2021)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Deeksha et al., 2018)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Dubey et al., 2020)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Engelbrecht et al., 2022)	P.D.	N/A	Y	N
(Guna et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Gunawan et al., 2021)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	N
(Selvakumar et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Hojjati et al., 2022)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Jacob et al., 2019)	IoT	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Jacobsen et al., 2020)	C.S.	Mixed	Y	Y
(Jain et al., 2023)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Jain et al., 2019)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Jimeno et al., 2021)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Kamrul et al., 2021)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019)	S.D.	N/A	N	Y
(Leon et al., 2020)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Likotiko et al., 2023)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	N
(Longo et al., 2021)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Makhseed et al., 2021)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Maulana et al., 2018)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Misra et al., 2018)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Mithinti et al., 2019)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Mohamed et al., 2023)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Mohammed et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Mohiuddin et al., 2021)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Moni et al., 2022)	IoT	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Mustapha et al., 2021)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Nafiz et al., 2023)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Pagar et al., 2022)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Pan et al., 2018)	C.S.	Mixed	Y	Y
(Papalambrou et al., 2015)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Pereira et al., 2019)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Poddar et al., 2017)	P.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Prasad et al., 2018)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Praveen et al., 2020)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Premgi et al., 2019)	S.I.	Indoors	Y	N
(Ramson et al., 2022)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Rohit et al., 2018)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Sai et al., 2023)	S.I.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Sampedro et al., 2021)	S.D.	N/A	Y	Y
(Shamin et al., 2019)	P.D.	Indoors	Y	Y
(Shanthini et al., 2022)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Sheng et al., 2020)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Singh et al., 2019)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Sirawattananon et al., 2021)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Suresh et al., 2020)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Tamakloe & Rosca, 2020)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	Y
(Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017)	P.D.	Mixed	Y	Y
(Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022)	S.D.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Widiastivi & Satria, 2020)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Wijaya et al., 2017)	P.D.	Outdoors	Y	N

(continued on next page)

Table 5 (continued)

Citation	Cat.	Env.	Sensing	Act.
(Kenya et al., 2020)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Yadav et al., 2022)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Zebua et al., 2022)	P.D.	Mixed	Y	Y
(Zhao et al., 2017)	P.D.	N/A	Y	N
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2023)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Ziouzios et al., 2021)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2019)	C.S.	Outdoors	Y	N

potential to serve as a foundational exploration for the optimal integration of distinct sensing modules into smart bins, thus contributing to the novelty of the field. In the work of Sai et al. (2023), the utilization of an ultrasound sensor is investigated to determine and monitor the fill level of a conventional trash can. Premgi et al. (2019) introduced a custom-made, low-cost infrared for the same purpose, highlighting its benefits and drawbacks accordingly. Aravindaraman and Ranjana (2019) examined the combination of an ultrasound sensor with a gas detector to monitor bin fill status in conjunction with the accumulation of carbon monoxide. Das et al. (2021) expanded on a three-sensor combination, using ultrasound with a load cell to monitor content levels and a humidity sensor to detect a buildup of wet waste.

4.1.4. Case study (20 %)

This group shifted the research focus from prototype development to the practical deployment of smart bins in various locations. Within this category, most applications emphasized routing optimization to support efficient collection services (Burman et al., 2022; Misra et al., 2018; Mustapha et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2018; Papalambrou et al., 2015; Suresh et al., 2020; Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2019). Some studies referenced live bin monitoring with alert generation, but did not provide further insights on waste collection strategies (Widiastiwi & Satria, 2020; Yadav et al., 2022). Jacobsen et al. (2020) introduced a device deployed in three separate locations, aiming to gather data on deposited trash for the development of an urban waste database. Meanwhile, Ziouzios and Dasygenis (2019), Ziouzios et al. (2021) and Ziouzios and Dasygenis (2023) conducted three pertinent studies in Western Macedonia, centered on waste classification, bin monitoring with AI-based prediction. In all of these cases, fill-level sensing was implemented on the bins, while additional functionalities remained relatively limited.

4.1.5. IoT application (8 %)

Concentrated specifically on the IoT aspect of certain use cases, the papers in this category exclusively focused on cases with fill-level sensing (Ali et al., 2020; Alwis et al., 2022; Badotra et al., 2021). Some instances also included user approach alert functionalities (Badotra et al., 2021; Jacob et al., 2019; Moni et al., 2022). Although this category could be considered a subset of the Case study group, it is

Fig. 2. Distribution of waste sorting categories in encountered relevant cases.

viewed separately as it placed greater emphasis on the communication and data transmission aspect, without explicitly mentioning or analyzing deployment or prototype development.

4.2. Descriptive analysis

By analyzing the definitive set of 79 publications, covering the span of the last 15 years, a remarkable trend emerges. Over 50 % of these publications surfaced between 2020 and 2023, emphasizing the novel and emerging nature of smart bin applications in urban waste management. The data presented in Table 5 further reinforce this trend, as 82 % of the articles were confined to a 5-year window, with 92 % encompassed within a 6-year period. For a visual representation of the age profile, refer to 2. With regard to the types of publication, 82 % of the selected articles were sourced from conferences, while the remaining 18 % were published in scientific journals (Fig. 2).

Considering the technical overview of smart bins, research findings indicate that approximately 37 % of the articles discussed outdoor-placed containers, while indoor cases accounted for around 30 % and just a small percentage of 6 % referred to mixed placements in both indoor and outdoor locations. Interestingly, a significant proportion of articles, approximately 27 % of the total cases, did not explicitly clarify the placement location of the bins.

The vast majority of cases (99 %) demonstrated sensing capabilities in various forms, while 63 % showcased actuating capabilities. An overwhelming 95 % of instances exhibited IoT compatibility, while the presence of artificial intelligence was evident in 33 % of the cases. Trash compaction, as a subset of actuation, was encountered in 8 % of the papers, while no shredding capabilities were observed in any of the cases.

With consideration to waste separation, approximately 46 % of the described cases involved some level of separation, either performed manually or through automation. The study identified five main categories of waste input approaches, with mixed waste input being the most commonly employed method. Specifically, only 6 % of the cases focused solely on recyclables, while 3 % addressed e-waste disposal. The remaining 2 % were equally divided between organic refuse and metallic objects.

A noteworthy observation was made regarding the trash separation functionalities in smart bins. In 92 % of the cases that demonstrated such capabilities, the trash input was in the form of a single item at a time. However, in the distinct 3 cases (Dubey et al., 2020; Jacob et al., 2019; Poddar et al., 2017), constituting the remaining 8 %, the containers received mixed waste input. Interestingly, in these particular instances, either the level of automation was significantly low, requiring manual pre-classification or in-situ sorting by the user (Dubey et al., 2020), or the concept maturity was at a low stage (Jacob et al., 2019; Poddar et al., 2017).

Regarding concept maturity, a rough division into three levels was established, taking into consideration the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) definition by Héder (2017). Although explicit TRLs are not mentioned in the selected publications, an overall picture was derived for each case from the articles. The three levels are defined as follows:

1. Low: Early concepts, TRLs roughly between 1 and 3.

Fig. 3. Concept maturity distribution overall and in cases with sorting capabilities.

Fig. 4. Distribution of waste sorting categories in encountered relevant cases.

2. *Medium*: More advanced concepts, with TRLs estimated around 4 to 6.
3. *High*: Concepts with solutions that are in a deployable state, with TRLs at 7 and 8.

Among the cases analyzed, 48 % of the applications employed *Low* maturity prototypes, which mainly consisted of proof-of-concept models made from cardboard or featuring simple sensor circuits and micro-controllers positioned in specific locations using provisional or ad hoc fastenings. *Medium* maturity level prototypes, accounting for approximately 32 % of the cases, were constructed from wood and incorporated relatively more sophisticated electronic circuits, subsystems, and housings. *High* maturity level prototypes were less common, making up only 20 % of the total cases. These instances showcased prototype assemblies with custom-made components or adaptations of standard urban waste

disposal containers to accommodate the sensors. Considering the subset of cases involving waste sorting functionalities, the distribution of maturity levels differed slightly. The most notable deviation refers to *High* maturity level prototypes which in this subset constituted merely 11 % of the total instances (Fig. 3).

Among the standout instances, with a focus on those demonstrating sorting capabilities, [Dubey et al. \(2020\)](#) implemented a multi-sensory module on standard residential waste bins, monitoring fill levels of manually deposited metal, wood, and plastic waste, along with poisonous gas levels. Their approach leveraged a Raspberry Pi to communicate with sensors and employed machine learning for fill-level prediction and collection scheduling optimization. [Shanthini et al. \(2022\)](#) showcased a multiple-rack prototype enabling manual sorting of food, cans, plastic, and non-recyclable waste, featuring a custom electronics board and ultrasound sensors for fill-level monitoring. [Longo](#)

et al. (2021) developed a smart bin prototype with single-item classification and segregation capabilities, utilizing optical means and a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifier for sorting, alongside ToF sensors for fill-level monitoring and Raspberry Pi for control. Wahyu-tama and Hwang (2022) presented a subsystem for waste container classification and capacity monitoring, integrating webcam-based object recognition with You Only Look Once (YOLO) library, coupled with a compartmentalized routing mechanism activated by identified trash, and a monitoring mobile app for location tracking and communication. These studies collectively highlight diverse approaches toward efficient waste sorting and management, each leveraging distinct technologies and methodologies.

4.3. Thematic analysis

This section makes use of the extracted and synthesized data to address the formulated research questions directly. The first part of the analysis concentrates on the comprehensive review of sensors and actuators found in the existing literature pertaining to smart bins, providing insight into their specific roles and functions. Subsequently, the second part investigates waste separation capabilities, starting with an exploration of classification techniques and following up with the examination of various physical separation mechanisms encountered in the literature.

4.3.1. Research question 1: What sensing and actuating technologies are utilized in smart bins for urban waste management?

This question encompasses two distinct components. The first component pertains to the diverse sensing solutions applied to smart bins. The second component explores the various actuation technologies employed for their specific purposes.

4.3.1.1. Sensing technologies. Investigating the sensing capabilities of smart bins, this study identified and presented a comprehensive taxonomy of 7 main sensing categories as shown in 4 The analysis was based on data extracted from Table 6 and encompassed various sensing methods found in the literature (Fig. 4).

4.3.1.1.1. Fill level sensing (84 %). The most predominant sensing type, involved monitoring the fill status of the bin. Further examination revealed that 90 % of the fill-level sensing implementations employed ultrasound sensors, while 6 % utilized Infrared (Burman et al., 2022; Chung et al., 2020; Premgi et al., 2019). Only 4 % adopted alternative technologies, such as time-of-flight laser sensors (Longo et al., 2021) and a custom vibration module (Zhao et al., 2017). Apart from fill level monitoring, an ultrasound sensor was also used as a means to detect a user approaching the bin and trigger automated lid opening (Zebua et al., 2022). Furthermore, Ahmed et al. (2022) utilized an infrared sensor after the entry point, to ensure the precise and effective disposal of trash while also providing timely alerts for potential congestion, thereby safeguarding the optimal functionality of the waste bin.

4.3.1.1.2. Gas detection (18 %). Regarding the integration of gas detectors, different approaches were investigated. In some instances, the assessment of carbon monoxide buildup was employed as a measure to evaluate the deterioration of organic waste (Amores et al., 2015). Moreover, Ahmed et al. (2022) and Misra et al. (2018) employed sensors capable of detecting ammonia levels to promptly seal the lid and prevent air contamination. Three other studies implemented gas sensors capable of detecting hydrocarbons such as methane and butane to mitigate health hazards associated with their emissions and potentially avert ignition incidents due to their flammable properties (Chung et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2019; Yadav et al., 2022).

4.3.1.1.3. Environment sensing (19 %). Regarding environmental monitoring, a variety of sensors for measuring humidity, temperature, and pressure were deployed in several instances. Specifically, humidity sensors, mainly cost-effective Digital Humidity and Temperature (DHT)

series models, were most frequently employed to detect moisture levels within the container (Als bou et al., 2018; Antora et al., 2022; Bhuvanewari et al., 2022; Boubaris et al., 2022; Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022; Chung et al., 2020; Das et al., 2021; Selvakumar et al., 2022; Likotiko et al., 2023; Misra et al., 2018; Mustapha et al., 2021; Sirawattananon et al., 2021). In the work of Sirawattananon et al. (2021), a raindrop sensor was utilized in conjunction with an automated lid to prevent water from entering the bin from outside. Additionally, Bhuvanewari et al. (2022) and Ziouzos and Dasygenis (2019) installed temperature sensors within the container as fire prevention tools, capable of detecting when the temperature exceeded predefined thresholds.

Lastly, two studies utilized a more advanced sensing solution, incorporating most of the above functions, measuring relative temperature, pressure, and humidity, as well as overall air quality with a single sensing module to monitor garbage degradation, moisture levels and mitigate risks of fire (Hojjati et al., 2022; Pan et al., 2018).

4.3.1.1.4. Weight sensing (15 %). Twelve distinct cases, used load cells to monitor the overall weight of the contents of the bin (Als bou et al., 2018; Azarudeen et al., 2021; Das et al., 2021; Engelbrecht et al., 2022; Guna et al., 2022; Gunawan et al., 2021; Kamrul et al., 2021; Likotiko et al., 2023; Maulana et al., 2018; Misra et al., 2018; Wijaya et al., 2017; Zebua et al., 2022). Their purpose was to directly alert collection crews, coupled with capacity level sensors in cases where, even though the fill level remained relatively low, the presence of dense items such as metal scraps would mandate early container vacation.

4.3.1.1.5. Composition (15 %). In order to discern information regarding the composition of deposited items, additional sensing solutions were employed. Inductive proximity sensors were integrated into 8 distinct prototypes (Azarudeen et al., 2021; Balbin et al., 2021; Bhuvanewari et al., 2022; Selvakumar et al., 2022; Kamrul et al., 2021; Leon et al., 2020; Makhseed et al., 2021; Maulana et al., 2018). Their primary function in each application was metal detection, specifically utilized in applications involving material sorting. Similarly, capacitance-type proximity sensors were also employed in 5 studies. Indicatively, Chung et al. (2020) utilized capacitance sensors to categorize waste as recyclable or non-recyclable by analyzing electrical permittivity values. In the work of Maulana et al. (2018), a capacitive sensor was combined with an inductive sensor to identify waste as glass, plastic, or paper. This same combination was also employed in two other studies to classify waste as paper or plastic (Leon et al., 2020; Makhseed et al., 2021). Conversely, Balbin et al. (2021) adopted an alternative approach, using the measurements to detect increased moisture levels in the container, effectively employing the capacitive sensor as an alternative to a humidity sensor. Shanthini employed a color sensor to identify specific types of plastic, though its implementation relied on a simplifying assumption regarding the colors of the deposited plastic components (Shanthini et al., 2022). Moreover, Pereira et al. (2019) utilized infrared as a composition detector, employing fundamental principles of spectroscopy to determine if the deposited trash was polymer in nature by analyzing its absorptivity values.

4.3.1.1.6. Computer vision (23 %). In most applications that incorporated computer vision, the technology served as a tool for object classification, coupled with AI algorithms, specifically neural networks (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Baras et al., 2020; Burman et al., 2022; Dasari et al., 2021; Jain et al., 2023; Jimeno et al., 2021; Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019; Longo et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Pagar et al., 2022; Sampredo et al., 2021; Sheng et al., 2020; Wahyu-tama & Hwang, 2022). In a more limited aspect computer vision was used to support fill level estimation, using cameras with depth perception to estimate volumes of deposited refuse (Antora et al., 2022; Boubaris et al., 2022). Moreover, a standalone approach was also adopted in two cases, where computer vision was used without AI, directly scanning QR-codes on marked disposed items for waste annotation (Alwis et al., 2022; Engelbrecht et al., 2022).

4.3.1.1.7. RFID (3 %). Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology was also present in 5 smart bin cases. The protocol was either

used simply for communication purposes and data transfer (Papalambrou et al., 2015; Wijaya et al., 2017) or to identify the smart bin user (Guna et al., 2022; Poddar et al., 2017). In Maulana et al. (2018) RFID tags on the deposited waste were used to identify the type of disposed item.

4.3.1.2. Actuation technologies. Concerning actuation, the review findings exhibit a more constrained range in comparison to sensing. The study identified several actuation methodologies to introduce a level of automation in specific functionalities of intelligent waste bins. Within this domain, three primary categories of actuation were identified.

4.3.1.2.1. Lid control (28 %). This category encompasses instances where basic motorized solutions were employed to achieve automated lid control in smart bins, to enable contactless operation (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ahmed et al., 2022; Alsbou et al., 2018; Alwis et al., 2022; Badotra et al., 2021; Bhuvanawari et al., 2022; Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022; Guna et al., 2022; Jacob et al., 2019; Pagar et al., 2022; Pereira et al., 2019; Poddar et al., 2017; Prasad et al., 2018; Ramson et al., 2022; Rohit et al., 2018; Shamin et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2019; Zebua et al., 2022). Alternatively, certain implementations introduced automated locking mechanisms to ensure secure closure and deter unauthorized access to the container (Das et al., 2021; Selvakumar et al., 2022).

4.3.1.2.2. Waste routing (34 %). The narrative analysis revealed a substantial body among the selected literature showcasing mechanical waste routing solutions. In some applications, these solutions involved the utilization of motorized hinges to control the opening of multiple compartments, thereby enabling regulated entry of deposited trash (Antora et al., 2022; Azarudeen et al., 2021; Baras et al., 2020; Chung et al., 2020; Dasari et al., 2021; Jimeno et al., 2021; Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019; Leon et al., 2020; Maulana et al., 2018; Mohammed et al., 2022; Sampetro et al., 2021; Sirawattananon et al., 2021; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017). Alternative approaches featured rotary mechanisms that relied on precise alignment of the entry compartment with the corresponding sub-compartment (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Balbin et al., 2021; Bhuvanawari et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2023, 2019; Kamrul et al., 2021; Longo et al., 2021) Alternatively, linear configurations employing conveyor belts coupled with lateral linear actuators were employed to direct the sorted trash accurately into their respective bins (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ayi-Annum et al., 2022; Selvakumar et al., 2022; Jacobsen et al., 2020; Makhseed et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2019).

4.3.1.2.3. Waste compaction (6 %). Compactor mechanisms were

incorporated in a limited number of studies to effectively reduce the fill level of the smart bins, thereby increasing their overall capacity and optimizing their storage efficiency (Chung et al., 2018, 2020; Singh et al., 2019; Tamakloe & Rosca, 2020).

4.3.1.2.4. Other (6 %). Despite its proximity to waste routing, the integration of a robotic arm for material handling and automated trash placement into various bins deviated significantly from all other routing solutions, warranting a separate categorization (Deeksha et al., 2018). Furthermore, in the study published by Anbumani et al. (2021) mentioned in the narrative analysis, a wheeled setup was employed to create a mobile bin capable of traversing its surrounding space, with the ultimate goal of developing an autonomous waste self-collection system.

Within the framework of motor-driven functionalities in smart waste containers, a variety of actuation devices were generally employed. DC motors were commonly used for continuous motion tasks that did not require high precision, while stepper motors were favored for more accurate and controlled movements, especially where alignment was aimed. For simple on-off motions such as control of lid and compartment entry points, small DC-based servos were the preferred choice due to their ease of control and cost-effectiveness. Regarding the encountered linear actuation mechanisms, the exact motors that were utilized were not explicitly specified, however, a common solution to achieve similar motion involves the use of electromagnetic solenoids.

4.3.2. Research question 2: What segregation capabilities are offered by the currently employed solutions with regard to smart bins for urban waste management?

In the context of waste sorting, the overall process involves two distinct stages. Initially, the deposited waste must be categorized into distinct materials or primary groups, such as recyclable or biodegradable items. Following this classification, the physical separation of the constituents must occur to achieve complete segregation.

4.3.2.1. Waste classification. An initial categorization regarding classification has been presented in Section 4.2. A more comprehensive investigation into the sorting capabilities of smart bins revealed a total of 14 main categories of distinct sorting methods, which are illustrated in Fig. 5 along with their corresponding distributions based on data extracted from Table 6 in selected papers. The percentages refer to the occurrence of the specific classification scenario among the 36 instances that exhibited waste sorting functionalities.

4.3.2.1.1. Metal (47 %). The primary material targeted for separation, appearing in almost half of the cases, is metallic waste.

Fig. 5. Distribution of waste sorting categories in encountered relevant cases.

Classification of metallic waste is predominantly either carried out using visual object recognition (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ayi-Annum et al., 2022; Baras et al., 2020; Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2019; Konstantinidis, Mouroutsos, & Gasteratos, 2021; Longo et al., 2021; Nafiz et al., 2023; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017) or with the use of inductive proximity sensors (Bhuvaneswari et al., 2022; Deeksha et al., 2018; Selvakumar et al., 2022; Jacobsen et al., 2020; Jain et al., 2023; Kamrul et al., 2021; Leon et al., 2020; Makhseed et al., 2021). Alternatively, in two cases metallic waste was manually annotated by the user (Dubey et al., 2020; Jain et al., 2019).

4.3.2.1.2. Plastic (44 %). A popular category as well, plastic waste grouping involves waste classification mainly through visual inspection and object recognition. Visual inspection (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Baras et al., 2020; Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022; Dasari et al., 2021; Mohammed et al., 2022; Nafiz et al., 2023; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017). A single case presented manual annotation of plastic refuse by the user (Dubey et al., 2020). Maulana et al. (2018) employed an RFID reader to scan marked components for subsequent categorization. Leon et al. (2020) used a combination of inductive sensors and limit switches to determine the type of liquid container, from a small range of pre-specified materials thus identifying plastic cups by excluding metal cans and paper cups. Makhseed et al. (2021) relied on a color sensor to recognize plastic parts, though this concept heavily relied on an assumption that all deposited plastics would be similarly colored. A rather interesting approach by Pereira et al. (2019), as mentioned in Section 4.3.1 implemented an Infrared sensor to discern plastic trash in a spectroscopy-based approach. No investigated studies presented methodologies to differentiate among different types of polymer.

4.3.2.1.3. Glass (28 %). Glass waste identification was present in approximately one out of three relevant instances. In nearly all occurrences, glass refuse was identified through computer vision (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Ayi-Annum et al., 2022; Baras et al., 2020; Longo et al., 2021; Makhseed et al., 2021; Mohammed et al., 2022; Nafiz et al., 2023; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017). (Papalambrou et al., 2015) focused mainly on detecting the shapes of deposited bottles, therefore segregating glass from other types of containers. No composition-based sensing technologies were observed in this group.

4.3.2.1.4. Dry/wet waste (25 %). Wet waste detection was achieved via humidity sensors positioned in the interior of the bin, or the entry point of the trash to determine the relative increase in moisture levels, thus indicating the presence of damp matter (Bhuvaneswari et al., 2022; Das et al., 2021; Deeksha et al., 2018; Jain et al., 2019; Shamin et al., 2019; Sirawattananon et al., 2021). Alternatively, some cases opted to use capacitance-type proximity sensors to track the higher dielectric constant of the liquid content in wet waste (Balbin et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2019).

4.3.2.1.5. Recyclable/non-recyclable (19 %). In this class of studies, recyclable and non-recyclable wastes were treated as whole categories, despite containing subsets comprising various materials. The classification of these waste categories was predominantly achieved through visual means and object recognition (Jacobsen et al., 2020; Konstantinidis, Kansizoglou, et al., 2021; Maulana et al., 2018; Pan et al., 2018; Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022). One article proposed a solution involving the manual sorting of recyclable waste by the user directly into separate compartments within the bin (Shanthini et al., 2022). Another study introduced a smart bin designed exclusively for recyclables, utilizing a humidity sensor to segregate wet items from the rest (Singh et al., 2019). Furthermore, a prototype developed by Chung et al. (2020) indicated that the distinction between recyclable and non-recyclable waste was accomplished using a capacitance sensor, which evaluated the dielectric properties of the trash. However, no further details were provided concerning this specific method in the prototype.

4.3.2.1.6. Paper/cardboard (19 %). This subset falls under recyclable waste, though in the selected studies is frequently encountered separately. The identification of paper or cardboard pieces of garbage is primarily achieved through optical means (Baras et al., 2020;

Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022; Longo et al., 2021; Mohammed et al., 2022). A single study uses trash marking and RFID to recognize paper (Maulana et al., 2018). Interestingly, two rather unconventional approaches were also explored, using a combination of inductive sensors to exclude metals and load cells or mechanical switches to detect light-weight paper parts (Azarudeen et al., 2021; Leon et al., 2020). However, it should be noted that these approaches required very specific waste inputs and would not function effectively in scenarios where mixed inputs are present.

4.3.2.1.7. Biodegradable/non-biodegradable (11 %). Biodegradable waste is a broad category that is encountered in a limited number of publications without further detailed breakdown. Chung et al. (2018) proposes the manual separation of biodegradable waste as a method. On the other hand, both Jimeno et al. (2021) and Pagar et al. (2022) utilize a camera and AI for visual classification of biodegradable waste. Additionally, Selvakumar et al. (2022) employs a combination of inductive and capacitive sensors, along with a humidity sensor, to effectively distinguish biodegradable garbage from plastics.

4.3.2.1.8. e-Waste (11 %). Electronics waste is not commonly encountered in smart bins. The only classification method observed in this case was visual recognition. More specifically Nafiz et al. (2023) and Pereira et al. (2019) utilized a camera module coupled with convoluted neural networks to identify and accordingly dispose of e-waste. Sampedro et al. (2021) and Antora et al. (2022) presented more focused approaches, using cameras with depth perception to discern specific e-waste items, such as cellphones, chargers, and batteries.

4.3.2.1.9. Organic (8 %). Organic waste detection was detected in two instances and was carried out exclusively using machine vision (Nafiz et al., 2023; Pereira et al., 2019). In certain instances, organic refuse was not specifically targeted for identification or sorting. Instead, it remained after excluding various other types of trash that were of more immediate interest. Consequently, the organic waste was disposed of in general waste compartments along with other uncategorized garbage (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Dasari et al., 2021; Jimeno et al., 2021).

4.3.2.1.10. Mixed (6 %). Two studies mentioned mixed waste classification. In these cases, visual waste categorization targeted recyclable materials such as paper, plastic, and glass. The remaining waste was classified as mixed and disposed of in a separate waste container (Baras et al., 2020; Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022).

4.3.2.1.11. Wood (3 %). By examining relevant studies, only a single case mentioned wood classification. The categorization technique utilized to do this was the manual annotation of the deposited waste (Dubey et al., 2020), meaning that no sensor-based technique was observed to distinguish wooden waste.

The majority of waste categorization was carried out using cameras and object recognition, accounting for 53 % of all classification cases. However, there were notable combinations of classification techniques other than vision-based approaches that emerged in the literature. Two distinct articles introduced the use of inductive and capacitive sensors for metal and wet waste classification, respectively (Balbin et al., 2021; Bhuvaneswari et al., 2022). In Kokoulin and Kiryanov (2019), an inductive sensor was combined with limit switches to identify different containers, tracing metal in cans and the overall dimensions of paper cups and bottles. Similarly, Kamrul et al. (2021) utilized an inductive sensor with a load cell to exclude metals and estimate the item material based on its weight and overall dimensions. Furthermore, a unique strategy was employed in Makhseed et al. (2021), where a combination of sensors was integrated onto a conveyor belt for in-situ classification of waste items, followed by subsequent physical separation.

4.3.2.2. Physical separation. Upon categorizing the introduced waste, a mechanism for the physical separation of the deposited items becomes necessary to finalize the sorting process. Based on the insights drawn from the examined articles, this stage is accomplished either through

Fig. 6. Proposed smart bin concept. a) Front view exterior, b) Front view interior, c) Top view interior.

manual intervention or by automated means.

4.3.2.2.1. Manual separation (11 %). In 4 out of 36 cases where waste separation was observed, the sorting was performed manually by the user. In Chung et al. (2020) a setup including two separate bins was used, where the user deposited self-classified biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste accordingly. Similarly Dubey et al. (2020) utilized a multi-bin configuration for the manual discarding of metal, wooden, and plastic parts. Shanthini et al. (2022) employed a system consisting of 3 separate bins on a single rack to facilitate manual sorting of food waste, metal and plastic cans, and non-recyclable refuse.

4.3.2.2.2. Automated separation (89 %). The majority of cases in the study exhibited various degrees of automation in waste separation. Whyutama and Hwang (2022) presented an automation-assisted approach, where the user optically scanned their waste and the bin used a rotary mechanism to internally align and open the appropriate compartment for the user to dispose of the item.

Most other approaches used gravity-fed sorting schemes, where the trash was inserted through a designated entry point and followed a vertical descent. At this stage, the discarded objects would be sorted using either a diverting mechanism, such as mechanical flipping bars which altered the trajectory of the fall, or servo-controlled compartment lids for flow control (Antora et al., 2022; Azarudeen et al., 2021; Baras et al., 2020; Chung et al., 2020; Dasari et al., 2021; Jimeno et al., 2021; Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019; Leon et al., 2020; Maulana et al., 2018; Mohammed et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2019; Sirawattananon et al., 2021; Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017). Alternatively, rotary mechanisms would align the entry point with the correct compartment (Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020; Balbin et al., 2021; Bhuvanawari et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2023, 2019; Kamrul et al., 2021; Longo et al., 2021).

Certain applications employed horizontal layouts, using conveyor belts to circulate the classified waste and actuators such as pistons to divert the trash to specifically designated buckets. Selvakumar et al. (2022) presented a prototype where a combination of sensors categorized inserted trash by composition as metal, biodegradable, and non-biodegradable items, and a rotating arm routed the garbage accordingly to either a bin or two conveyor belts. Jacobsen et al. (2020) used a vision-based classifier to discern between recyclable and non-recyclable objects. The user would dispose of their item at an entry point on top of a conveyor belt. The classifier would annotate the waste and subsequently move the belt left or right for the item to end up inside one of two bins. In Makhseed et al. (2021) the deposited trash, classified into glass, plastic, metal, or “other” using a composition-based set of sensors would

traverse on a conveyor belt and pistons would push them laterally into one of 4 bins. Nafiz et al. (2023) employed a similar approach, using a vision-based classification module with a camera and a neural network to produce an expanded categorization, and 6 bins to deposit e-waste, glass, metal, and plastic waste, as well as organic and medical refuse.

In a previously noted application by Deeksha et al. (2018), a robot arm was used for material handling, sorting deposited waste in multiple bins, showing promising potential. However, it was acknowledged that further advancements would be necessary to fully realize its capabilities and increase its maturity.

5. Discussion

5.1. Key outputs from analyzing the research questions

The examined literature on smart bins showcases a diverse array of sensing technologies, with a predominant focus on monitoring bin fill status level and ensuring IoT compatibility. These two criteria emerge consistently across most studies, often standing alone as the main factors for smart bin qualification. Fill level measuring, which is featured prominently across the vast majority of examined studies. This technology proves instrumental in enabling smart bins to monitor trash volumes, thereby optimizing collection schedules. Strategic adjustments in collection frequency and scheduling hold the potential for substantial energy conservation and cost reduction in urban environments, considering factors such as energy consumption (Balakera et al., 2024) and crew expenses. Ultrasound sensors, in particular, dominate the fill level measuring landscape due to their apparent reliability, cost-effectiveness, and immunity to disturbances from lighting conditions—an issue commonly encountered by IR sensors and vision ones (Sifnaios et al., 2023).

Exploring less common sensing approaches, such as gas and environment sensors, emerges with a more targeted role, appearing in approximately 1 out of 5 examined cases. These sensors are primarily associated with organic waste and degradation issues. Weight appears to play a less significant role, being substituted in most cases by volume monitoring instead, by using fill-level sensing. Lastly, while sporadic mentions of other sensor types are also found in various articles, their integration appears highly case-specific and lacks a standardized presence. For example, composition identification and RFID, are present but to a limited extent, being more prevalent in studies focused on sorting-capable smart bins.

An intriguing trend related to classification mechanisms has surfaced. Two primary approaches for classification were encountered. The first method utilizes cameras, computer vision, and data, either generated during the studies or sourced from existing databases. While this approach stands out as the most popular solution out of the two for waste classification, its implementation is hindered by high associated costs. Machine vision, often AI-driven, necessitates the additional integration of control units into bins, contributing to an overall cost increase that may pose challenges for their widespread adoption. The second approach relies on sensor-based classification, specifically targeting waste composition. Notably, induction-based sensing is used for metal identification, while humidity or capacitive sensing is employed for distinguishing dry and wet waste. However, the combination of both approaches, which could enable more advanced sorting schemes, has not been observed in any of the investigated studies. It is worth mentioning that advanced composition-based methods, such as the use of spectroscopy, are notably limited in the context of bin-level applications. Only one study among the selected articles explored such techniques, even though spectroscopy techniques such as FTIR are known to be employed for similar purposes in other applications (Shengli et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2019). The reasons for this shortcoming could also be attributed to the high costs associated with advanced spectrometry techniques. One primary factor contributing to their underutilization is the substantial implementation costs associated with these subsystems. Spectroscopy-based sensors are usually relatively expensive compared to optical devices, ranging from several hundred euros to several thousand for more elaborate applications. The sophisticated nature of automated actuation systems necessitates significant investment as well, both in terms of hardware and software components. Moreover, the design and programming intricacies accompanying these technologies pose additional challenges. Mechanical actuation, for instance, demands meticulous mechatronics design and programming to ensure not only compliant output but also safety standards adherence. As a result, despite their potential benefits in enhancing waste management efficiency and accuracy, the high upfront costs and complex design considerations have hindered the widespread adoption and exploration of these advanced technologies within the smart bins domain. Nevertheless, incorporating in-situ waste classification at an early stage could prove advantageous for urban waste management by facilitating effective waste separation. In that sense, a cost-benefit analysis of using more advanced classification techniques or elaborate sensor combinations ought to prove essential to maximize the usefulness of a new generation of smart bins.

Although various forms of waste separation using smart bins have been developed, the majority of these solutions are limited to single-item sorting, and no instances of real-time automated separation of mixed waste inputs were observed. While different separation scenarios were evident, such as multiple compartments with controllable lids, or conveyor belts to circulate disposed items, a comprehensive solution that incorporates a wide range of separation capabilities remains elusive. Furthermore, within the waste sorting domain, only a few concepts have reached a high level of maturity, as observed in 3. More than half of the investigated cases resulted in highly provisional and experimental prototypes, not yet suitable for full-scale deployment. On the other hand, among the cases that did exhibit deployment for operation in relevant environments, only a minimal number of sensors and sorting capabilities were tested, providing limited data on their efficiency and overall benefits.

A comprehensive quantified demonstration of the benefits resulting from the deployment of smart bins appears to be limited, potentially due to the current scarcity of highly mature solutions and a lack of available information on cost ranges for developed prototypes. Additionally, the literature search did not yield any solutions at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 9, which is expected, as solutions that reach this level of maturity tend to transition to patents and commercialization. Nonetheless, it underscores the need for further research on commercially

available smart bins for supplementary comparison and to achieve a comprehensive state-of-the-art mapping in the field.

5.2. Proposed framework

Following the analysis of existing solutions in related academic literature, a novel smart bin concept is presented to address identified gaps. The proposed framework takes the form of a reverse vending machine capable of accommodating multiple-waste entry and automated in-situ separation.

In this setup Fig. 6, users deposit their mixed waste through a designated entry point, where a motorized conveyor-based module enables internal waste circulation. The waste stream is then processed by an AI-driven object recognition and classification module, incorporating a camera and a combination of inductive and capacitive proximity sensors to identify metal and wet items respectively. Additionally, a FTIR module is incorporated to detect plastic waste, further enabling differentiation among specific types of plastic. Categorized items are extracted from the conveyor by a robot-based actuation system, utilizing mechanical and pneumatic displacement, and placed in individual containers for each major category (e.g., metal waste, plastic, cardboard, bottles). Unidentified waste is directed into a general waste container at the conveyor line's end.

Each individual container features a load cell for constant weight monitoring and an ultrasound sensor for fill-level surveillance, with compaction mechanisms integrated to increase overall capacity. Shredding modules can be added over specific containers, such as those receiving plastic, to further reduce trash volume. To enhance monitoring, a BME680 sensor is included in the interior of the smart bin to track temperature, humidity, and air quality. Data from integrated sensors are transmitted via WIFI for analysis, with control and synchronization of all actuation systems managed by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) for robust signal processing.

The proposed concept is anticipated to provide numerous benefits compared to existing instances. Firstly, it offers compatibility with multiple-waste entry, a feature seldom encountered in the examined literature. This capability is bolstered by sophisticated automated circulation and actuation mechanisms. The extensive array of sensors and connectivity modules is carefully chosen to address a wide range of sensing requirements. Fill-level sensing, weight monitoring, and environmental condition observation are crucial for optimizing collection scheduling. Moreover, the identification of waste composition, facilitated by induction and capacitance sensing, in conjunction with AI object recognition and FTIR, can significantly enhance the accuracy of detecting specific types of waste, such as metal and plastic disposed objects.

The concept finally prioritizes modularity, allowing for customization during the design stage by adjusting conveyor length and the number of individual buckets to accommodate various waste management scenarios. Sensor types can also be flexibly tailored based on specific segregation requirements. To facilitate efficient waste collection, all utilized individual containers are standardized wheelie bins, easily removable by collection crews through an opening in the front of the device.

6. Conclusions

Through a comprehensive review of academic literature, the current state of smart bins was investigated, with a particular focus on those equipped with waste sorting capabilities. Results highlighted the technologies integrated in smart bins in research over the past 15 years. The most and least common technologies concerning sensing and actuation were presented, summarized, and discussed. The main findings can be summarized in the following points:

- Smart bins showcase a diverse array of sensing solutions, though only a few, such as fill level sensing emerge as a recurrently encountered type.
- Despite ongoing waste classification efforts, advanced multisensory methods, combining machine vision and composition identification are yet to be extensively adopted.
- While smart bin concepts with integrated waste sorting capabilities exist, the majority remain at a basic level.
- An absence of common ground or standardization in sensing and actuating is evident.

Drawing upon the insights from the literature review, proposed future work involves conducting market research to identify comparable products, encompassing both sorting and non-sorting smart bins up to TRL9. Subsequently, a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis is recommended, evaluating the integration of advanced multisensory modules. The analysis should also encompass elaborate sorting capabilities as well to provide a more holistic approach to waste management at bin-level. Building upon these additional steps, a novel concept for an advanced intelligent waste disposal unit is proposed, aiming to create an efficient, multi-functional, and effective waste sorting system at a high level that addresses identified research gaps and aligns with evolving waste management requirements, tailored specifically for waste management within modern smart urban environments. Further development of this concept into a working prototype for testing and validation is also included in the suggested future work.

Appendix A

Table 6

Contextual information about the surveyed articles, including the type of sensing, type, and form of inserted waste, presence of compaction or shredding capabilities, and concept maturity level. In the sensing type column abbreviations are adopted for conciseness: FL refers to Fill Level, W to weight, G stands for Gas, ENV is for environment, UA means User approach, F and I refer to Fire and Item Insertion respectively. Lastly, C stands for Composition, V for Vision and RFID is used as is.

Citation	Sensing type	Actuation type	Waste type	Waste form	Waste sorting type	Compaction	Shredding	Concept maturity
(Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020)	FL	Lid control, Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Metal/ Plastic/ Glass/ Other	N	N	Medium
(Ahmed et al., 2022)	FL, I, G	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Ali et al., 2020)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Als bou et al., 2018)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Alwis et al., 2022)	FL	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Amores et al., 2015)	G	N/A	Organic	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Anbumani et al., 2021)	FL, G	Wheeled spatial motion	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Antora et al., 2022)	V	Compartment control	e-waste	Single item	Cellphone/ Charger/ Battery/ Other	N	N	Low
(Aravindaraman & Ranjana, 2019)	FL, G	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Ayi-Annum et al., 2022)	FL, V, I	Conveyor belt, sorting piston	Mixed	Single item	e-Waste/ Glass/ Metal/ Organic/ Plastic	N	N	Low
(Azarudeen et al., 2021)	FL	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Paper/ Plastic/ Other	N	N	Low
(Badotra et al., 2021)	FL	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Balbin et al., 2021)	C, I	Alignment rotation	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet/ Metal	N	N	Medium
(Baras et al., 2020)	FL, V	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Glass/ Metal/ Paper/ Plastic/ Mixed	N	N	Medium
(Bhuvanewari et al., 2022)	FL, ENV, C	Alignment rotation, Lid control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet/ Metal	N	N	Medium
(Boubaris et al., 2022)	UA, FL, G, F, ENV, V, RFID	Lock control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022)	FL, ENV, UA, V	Lid control	Mixed	Single item	Glass/ Metal/ Paper/ Plastic/ Mixed	N	N	Low

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Panagiotis Zoumpoulis: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Fotios K. Konstantinidis:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Georgios Tsimiklis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Angelos Amditis:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All relevant data are included in the manuscript. If more are required the authors will provide them upon request

Table 6 (continued)

Citation	Sensing type	Actuation type	Waste type	Waste form	Waste sorting type	Compaction	Shredding	Concept maturity
(Burman et al., 2022)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Chung et al., 2020)	FL, G, ENV	Comp. control, compaction	Mixed	Single item	Recyclable/Non-recyclable	Y	N	Low
(Chung et al., 2018)	FL	Compaction	Mixed	Single item	Biodeg./ Non-biodeg.	Y	N	Low
(Das et al., 2021)	FL, W, ENV	Servo control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet	N	N	Low
(Dasari et al., 2021)	FL	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Paper/ Plastic/ Other	N	N	Low
(Deeksha et al., 2018)	FL, ENV, C	Robot arm control	Mixed	Single item	Metal/ Dry/ Wet	N	N	Low
(Dubey et al., 2020)	FL, G	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	Metal/ Wood/ Plastic	N	N	High
(Engelbrecht et al., 2022)	UA, W, V	N/A	Recyclables	Single item	N/A	N	N	Low
(Guna et al., 2022)	FL, W, UA, RFID	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Gunawan et al., 2021)	FL, W	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Selvakumar et al., 2022)	FL, C, ENV	Conveyor belt, lid lock	Mixed	Multiple items	Biodeg./ Non-biodeg./ Metal	N	N	Low
(Hojjati et al., 2022)	FL, ENV, V	N/A	Mixed	Single item	N/A	N	N	High
(Jacob et al., 2019)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Jacobsen et al., 2020)	V	Conveyor belt	Mixed	Single item	General waste/ Recyclable	N	N	Medium
(Jain et al., 2023)	C, I	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet/ Metal	N	N	Medium
(Jain et al., 2019)	FL, C, ENV, I	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet/ Metal	N	N	Low
(Jimeno et al., 2021)	FL, V	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Biodeg./ Recyclable/ Other	N	N	Medium
(Kamrul et al., 2021)	I, C, W	Alignment rotation	Metals	Single item	Metal	N	N	Low
(Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019)	N/A	Sorting route control	Recyclables	Single item	Type of container (bottle, can)	Y	N	Low
(Leon et al., 2020)	C	Compaction, Comp. control	Recyclables	Single item	Plastic bottles/ Metal cans/ Paper cups	Y	N	Low
(Likotiko et al., 2023)	FL, G, ENV, W	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Longo et al., 2021)	FL, V	Alignment rotation	Mixed	Single item	Glass/ Paper/ Plastic/ Metal/ Other	N	N	High
(Makhseed et al., 2021)	I, C	Conveyor belt, side push sorter	Mixed	Single item	Glass/ Plastic/ Metal/ Other	N	N	Medium
(Maulana et al., 2018)	FL, C, W	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Glass/ Paper/ Plastic	N	N	Medium
(Misra et al., 2018)	FL, G	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Mithinti et al., 2019)	FL, W	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Mohamed et al., 2023)	FL, G	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Mohammed et al., 2022)	FL, C, W	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Gass/ Paper/ Plastic	N	N	Medium
(Mohiuddin et al., 2021)	FL, G	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Moni et al., 2022)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Mustapha et al., 2021)	FL, ENV, V	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Nafiz et al., 2023)	FL, V, I	Conveyor belt, side push sorter	Mixed	Single item	e-Waste/ Glass/ Metal/ Organic/ Plastic	N	N	Low
(Pagar et al., 2022)	FL, V	Lid control, sorting piston	Mixed	Single item	Biodeg./ Non-biodeg.	N	N	Low
(Pan et al., 2018)	V	Conveyor belt	Mixed	Single item	General waste/ Recyclable	N	N	Medium
(Papalambrou et al., 2015)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Pereira et al., 2019)	FL, C, ENV	Lid control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/ Wet/ Plastic	N	N	Medium
(Poddar et al., 2017)	FL, UA, ENV	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Prasad et al., 2018)	UA, FL	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Praveen et al., 2020)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Premgi et al., 2019)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Ramson et al., 2022)	FL, I, G	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Rohit et al., 2018)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Sai et al., 2023)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low

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Table 6 (continued)

Citation	Sensing type	Actuation type	Waste type	Waste form	Waste sorting type	Compaction	Shredding	Concept maturity
(Sampedro et al., 2021)	V	Compartment control	e-waste	Single item	Cellphone/ Charger/ Battery/ Other	N	N	Low
(Shamin et al., 2019)	FL, UA	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	Dry/ Wet/ Metal	N	N	Medium
(Shanthini et al., 2022)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Single item	Organic/ Cans/ Plastic/ non-recyclable	N	N	High
(Sheng et al., 2020)	FL, V	N/A	Mixed	Single item	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Singh et al., 2019)	FL,UA, ENV, G	Lid control, compaction	Mixed	Single item	Recyclable/ Non-recyclable	Y	N	Low
(Sirawattananon et al., 2021)	I, ENV	Compartment control	Mixed	Single item	Dry/Wet	N	N	Low
(Suresh et al., 2020)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Tamakloe & Rosca, 2020)	FL	Compaction	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	Y	N	Medium
(Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017)	FL, V	Compartment control	Recyclables	Single item	Metal/ Plastic/ Glass	N	N	Medium
(Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Single item	Organic/ Cans / Plastic/ Non-recyclable	N	N	High
(Widiastiwati & Satria, 2020)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Wijaya et al., 2017)	FL, W	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Xenya et al., 2020)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Yadav et al., 2022)	FL, W	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Zebua et al., 2022)	FL, W, G	Lid control	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Zhao et al., 2017)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	Low
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2023)	FL	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High
(Ziouzios et al., 2021)	FL, V	N/A	Recyclables	Single item	N/A	N	N	Medium
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2019)	FL, ENV, LS	N/A	Mixed	Multiple items	N/A	N	N	High

Table 7

Contextual information about the surveyed articles, including incorporated sensing and data transfer capabilities. In the “other sensors” type column abbreviations are adopted for conciseness. More specifically, Cap. stands for Capacitive and Ind. refers to Inductive.

Cit.	Fill-level sensor	Gas	Weight	Environment	Fire detection	RFID	IoT	AI	Computer vision	GPS/ GPRS	GSM	Other sensors
(Abeygunawardhana et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N
(Ahmed et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Infrared
(Ali et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Alsbou et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Alwis et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Amores et al., 2015)	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Anbumani et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Infrared
(Antora et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	RF card reader
(Aravindaraman & Ranjana, 2019)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N
(Ayi-Annum et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Azarudeen et al., 2021)	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Ind. sensor
(Badotra et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N
(Balbin et al., 2021)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Ind. & Cap. sensors
(Baras et al., 2020)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Bhuvaneswari et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Ind. sensor
(Boubaris et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	RF card reader
(Bourougaa-Tria et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Burman et al., 2022)	Infrared	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N
(Chung et al., 2020)	Infrared	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Cap. Sensor
(Chung et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Das et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Dasari et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Deeksha et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Infrared & Ind. Sensors
(Dubey et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N

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Table 7 (continued)

Cit.	Fill-level sensor	Gas	Weight	Environment	Fire detection	RFID	IoT	AI	Computer vision	GPS/GPRS	GSM	Other sensors
(Engelbrecht et al., 2022)	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
(Guna et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Gunawan et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Selvakumar et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Cap. & Ind. sensors
(Hojjati et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Jacob et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Jacobsen et al., 2020)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Jain et al., 2023)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N
(Jain et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
(Jimeno et al., 2021)	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Kamrul et al., 2021)	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Ind. sensor
(Kokoulin & Kiryanov, 2019)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N
(Leon et al., 2020)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Ind. sensor, limit switch
(Likotiko et al., 2023)	Infrared	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N
(Longo et al., 2021)	Laser	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Makhseed et al., 2021)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Ind., Cap. & Color sensors
(Maulana et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	Cap. & Ind. sensors
(Misra et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Mithinti et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Mohamed et al., 2023)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Mohammed et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N
(Mohiuddin et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Moni et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Mustapha et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N
(Nafiz et al., 2023)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N
(Pagar et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Pan et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Papalambrou et al., 2015)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Pereira et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Infrared & Cap. sensor
(Poddar et al., 2017)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Prasad et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Praveen et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Premgi et al., 2019)	Infrared	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Ramson et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Rohit et al., 2018)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Infrared
(Sai et al., 2023)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Sampedro et al., 2021)	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N
(Shamin et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Shanthini et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Sheng et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Singh et al., 2019)	Ultrasound	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Sirawattananon et al., 2021)	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Suresh et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Tamakloe & Rosca, 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Tiwari & Nagarathna, 2017)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Wahyutama & Hwang, 2022)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Widiastiwi & Satria, 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Wijaya et al., 2017)	Ultrasound	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N
(Xenya et al., 2020)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N
(Yadav et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Zebua et al., 2022)	Ultrasound	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Ultrasound (user approach)
(Zhao et al., 2017)	Vibration	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2023)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N
(Ziouzios et al., 2021)	Ultrasound	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
(Ziouzios & Dasygenis, 2019)	Ultrasound	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Pressure sensor

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